

Role of Local Government in Food Availability Based on Indonesia's Food Law in Serang City

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ABSTRACT: The authority in terms of food availability that has been mandated in Indonesia's food law said that the Central Government and Local Government are responsible for food availability. Units of Local Government are assigned by The Ministry of the Agriculture Republic of Indonesia to do their function and tasks in the food security field. Role of Serang City Government effort is needed for increasing food security. With literature research and field studies, it can be seen on the reality that Serang City does not have a specific institution yet to solve food security problems. Subsequently, all of these problems make the obligation of Serang's Agricultural Institution full. In this case, a specific food institution whose tackling food problems is needed.

KEYWORD: Food Availability, Food Security, Local Government.

INTRODUCTION

Indonesia is known as an agricultural country, most of its inhabitants work in agriculture. This situation should be a favorable thing for the Indonesian state because, with its vast green lands and biodiversity, it can make Indonesia a prosperous country and prosperous its citizens. A Country with a wide range of agricultural land, plantation, waters and representative forest. Every year 100,000 hectares of agricultural land shrinks, plantation productivity declines, waters yields decline due to the destruction of waters and decreasing forest area due to illegal logging and licensing systems both legal and illegal in Forest Management Rights that result in declining and even disappearing forest functions. Logically, as an agrarian country, Indonesia can meet the food which needed to its people properly and sustainably.¹ The problem of declining forest area is not the only one that can inhibit the fulfillment of food, but there are other problems such as population increase. This can be a serious threat to Indonesia, because with the increasing population will also increase the need for food, but it will also occur other problems in the environment sector. The problem will certainly affect to other sectors, not only the environment but also on the social and economic sectors. With the emergence of food-related problems, will lead to problems in the social sector that cause food scarcity if the economic sector disrupted such as the high demand for staple food, but the available food cannot meet the demand. This becomes a problem that needs to be resolved by the government as a responsibility in the prosperity of its citizens. This because Indonesia is a welfare state, in the welfare state the government's duty in organizing the public interest becomes very wide. Therefore, it is necessary for the freedom to move in the administration of the state in accordance with the authority given. With such authority, the government has responsibility for the welfare of its citizens, especially in the fulfillment of citizen's right to food.² Therefore, the government needs to establish an institution or agency that special moves in the field of food security. This institution should be integrated both at the central and regional levels because the problem of food security becomes a serious thing that must be considered by the government both central and regional.

Indonesia has 34 Provinces, Java Island has 10 Provinces. One of them is Banten Province. Banten Province consists of 8 districts/cities, one of which is the city of Serang. Serang city can be a reference for the City and other districts in Banten province, considering the city of Serang is the capital of Banten province. The increase in population especially in Serang City based on data from Central Bureau of Statistics (BPS), notes that the population growth rate in Serang City each year is 0.77 percent.³ The need for food makes the government issue a policy on food security because one of the government's authority in agriculture is the

¹Ikomatussuniah, *Swasembada Pangan Untuk Ketahanan Pangan*, <http://ikomatussuniah-design.blogspot.co.id/>, accessible on 07/07/2017, 07.17 WIB.

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determination of standard norms of procurement, management, and distribution of food.⁴ The availability of food is important in efforts to meet the food which needed to the people, especially the basic needs of the community along with the increasing population growth. A rise in global food prices could lead to an increasing number of starving citizens. Food shortages and malnutrition in a country will only leave the generation less intelligent, physically weak and less productive. So the need for food sovereignty development in Serang City. Food sovereignty is a way of achieving the welfare conceptualized in the welfare state in Indonesia, it is contained in the fourth paragraph of the Constitution of the Republic Indonesia 1945. Not only in the Constitution, food sovereignty has been enshrined in Indonesian food law. The law states that food sovereignty is the right of the state and the right of the nation to independently determine food policy to guarantee the right of food for the people. So the public has the right to determine the foods system in accordance with the potential of its local resources. Because in a country must be able to produce a variety of food, in fulfilling the right to food of its people up to individuals.⁵ The availability of food to meet which needed, the people's food becomes a matter that must be paid attention by the government in each region respectively. Because food availability is part of food security and food sovereignty.

Food security which is the task of the central government and each local government in their respective regions. As stated in Article 12 paragraph (1) and paragraph (2) of Law No. 18 of 2012 on Food has stated that the Government and local governments are responsible for the availability of food. And also states that the Government and local governments are responsible for the availability of food in the region and the development of local food production in the region. Local government, in this case, is the government of Serang City, has an obligation to prosper the community, especially sufficient food supply in Serang City. Local governments need to pay attention to food planning regularly also pay attention to the distribution of food and marketing. As a general welfare organizer, the government's duties include all social fields that are actively participating in government administration in public health, teaching, food and agrarian duties. Thus, state administrators have freedom of action, especially in the urgent circumstances that occur, while the settlement regulation which of course was not there.⁶ This also applies to local governments to assign a particular body or institution in the field of food in meeting the availability of food in the Serang City, because food security in the Serang City is the authority of the Government of Serang City.

The task of the local government related to the availability of food in the effort to fulfill the right to the food of the people has been regulated in Regulation the Minister of Agriculture Republic of Indonesia No. 43/Permentan/OT.010/8/2016 that in the settlement of food resilience issues, resolved by the Regional Device Work Unit (SKPD) Which specialized in handling food affairs. If the jurisdiction covers the district/city, then the SKPD is the Agency Food Security of District/City. So if in a jurisdiction there isn't SKPD that has been mandated by the Regulation of the Minister of Agriculture, it can be said that the Regional Government does not implement the provisions properly. And Serang City becomes the only City from all District/City in Banten Province which until now hasn't Food Security Institution. This shows that Serang City Government doesn't see the problem of food security as a matter of special concern, because how the Government of Serang City will implement the provisions of the Regulation of the Minister of Agriculture in terms of food availability to meet the food which needed by the community, in the absence of SKPD that specifically handles related issues of food security, which is essentially the fulfillment of the right to food is clearly a mandate in the Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia 1945. The formation of SKPD that specifically addresses food security issues can be done by the Government of Serang City, in fulfilling the right to food of the people in Serang City. This will also facilitate the Government in carrying out supervisory functions in the area for food security affairs. Considering the establishment of SKPD that specifically handles food security is also mandate in the Regulation the Minister of Agriculture Republic of Indonesia No. 43/Permentan/OT.010/8/2016 on the Guidelines of Nomenclature, Duties, and Functions of Food Affairs and the Institution of Agricultural Affairs of Provincial District/City. So with the establishment SKPD of food security, the Government of Serang City has carried out the mandate in the regulation.

Based on the background stated earlier, the core issue in this paper is the exposure related to the role of the Government of Serang City in the availability of food and how the constraints faced due to the absence of special Institution that handles food security problems in Serang City.

²Ikomatussuniah, *Class Action terhadap Utang Swasta Bantuan Likuidasi Bank Indonesia menjadi Utang Negara*, Jurnal Masalah-masalah Hukum, Vol. 42 No 3, 2013, Semarang, ISSN 2086- 2695, pages. 363.

³Badan Pusat Statistik, *Banten Dalam Angka 2016*, pages. 57.

⁴Christine S. T. Kansil, *Pemerintahan Daerah di Indonesia Hukum Administrasi Negara*, Sinar Grafika, Jakarta, 2004, pages. 132.

⁵Ikomatussuniah, *Letargi Harga Pangan*, Majalah Dinamika Kabupaten Serang, Vol. 40 No. 3 Dinamika Triwulan 3, 2016, Serang, pages. 38.

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RESEARCH METHOD

Approach method in this research is normative juridical approach refers to food law and juridical sociology which refers to a social condition that exists in society. This research is included in the type of descriptive analytical research because it describes the role of Serang City Government in the availability of food. Sources of data in this study are secondary data, secondary data sources are those that include bibliographic data, journals, scientific papers, articles and documents related to the research material. In addition to secondary data, researchers also use primary data sources as a source of supporting data in the form of interviews. In this research, the interview was conducted to Head of Food Institution of Agriculture of Serang City. Data that have been collected from the results of research and then analyzed qualitatively normative.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

1. Food Availability in Serang City

Food is a basic human need, and the state is obliged to realize the availability, reach, and fulfillment of adequate, safe, quality and balanced nutritious food consumption both nationally and regionally up to individuality in all regions of the Indonesian republic as well as in Serang City. This can be realized by the Government of Serang City by utilizing local resources owned by each sub-district, not only through local resources but also local institutions and culture in Serang City itself. Because Serang City is a region with a fairly dense population, based on the population census conducted by the Central Bureau of Statistics in 2015 is 643,205 inhabitants. While the total area of Serang City is 266.71 km², but on the other hand has diverse natural resources and food resources, if utilized as possible by the Government of Serang City and the community. Serang City, in essence, can meet which needs of the community for food sovereign and independent.⁷ This is also mentioned in article 1 of Law No. 18 of 2012 on Food, that food is anything derived from biological sources of agricultural products, plantations, forestry, fisheries, livestock, water, and water, both processed and unprocessed, Designated as food or beverage for human consumption, including food additives, foodstuffs, and other materials used in the process of preparing, processing, and/or making food or drink. In this sense, the definition of food is very broad, so it needs government involvement in it to meet which food needed for the community. Because food is an absolute right for every citizen.

Food availability in Article 1 point (6) of Government Regulation No. 17 of 2015 on Food Security and Nutrition, namely the condition of the availability of food from domestic production and national food reserves and imports of the two main sources cannot meet the needs. In order to meet the food supply, Serang City Government needs to pay attention to domestic production and national food reserves, then if the two food sources are not met then the efforts of Serang City Government to fulfill the food supply is to import food or food procurement from other areas. The availability of food can affect the livelihood of the community, both producers (farmers) and consumers. So that the people of Serang City and the state organizers have the right to determine their food security system independently. Food security is basically rooted in the fulfillment of food for households, which is reflected in the availability of adequate food, both in quantity and quality, safe, equitable, and affordable. Because there are three subsystems in food security, namely availability, access, and food absorption. The three subsystem must be met and related to each other, so that if one of the subsystems are not met then the food security can be said still fragile. Two main subsystems that must be realized by the Government of Serang City, in this case, is the availability of food and food access. For that, it needs to be thought that food security is more a massive system of two main interrelated subsystems, namely producers and production, and consumers and their consumption. Each food security subsystem is determined by the components that support each other, including the community and the organizer of food security itself.⁸

The local government is responsible for the availability of adequate food for the community, because the local government is committed to improving the welfare of the community, and it can start from improving the management of agricultural land, so that crops can increase, not only rice crops but also other crops such as corn and soybean Increased production. This is also an effort that needs to be done by the Government of Serang City in realizing the availability of food. Therefore, what can be done by the local government in this case is also the Government of Serang City is through food self-sufficiency program, this is a program that must be considered by the local government in addition to Human Development Index (HDI), thus through many industries entering into an area but agricultural land can be maintained.⁹ Thus the need for food can be met by the government, given the current population growth is quite rapid. The role of Serang City Government in realizing food availability is the authority received by attribution in Article 12 paragraph (2) of Law No. 18 of 2012 on Food, stated that the government and local government are responsible for the availability of food. The authority is owned by the Serang City Agriculture Institution. This is a mandate in Article 3 Sub-Article d of Serang City Regulation Number 7 of 2016 concerning the Establishment and Structuring of Serang City Regional Device, mentioning that the Agriculture Office organizes government affairs in agriculture, marine and fishery, and food field. In implementing food availability, the Serang City Agricultural Service can cooperate among other Institution in Serang City,

⁶R. Abdoel Djarnali, Pengantar Hukum Indonesia, Rajawali Pers, Jakarta, 2012, pages. 100.

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but its main duty and function are the authority possessed by the Serang City Agriculture Institution. With the appointment of Serang City Agriculture Office as SKPD that handles food security issues, this can make the main tasks and functions of the Serang City Agricultural Service more solid. Given that the problem of food security is not only based on problems in the agricultural sector but based on other sectors such as social and economic sectors. Because of the complexity of food security issues, and agriculture-related problems are also big problems. So that the Agriculture Office of Serang City will get a dense task if it has to deal with issues related to food security.

The availability of food in the effort to realize food security in Serang City should be carried out based on the mandate in article 12 of Law No. 18 of 2012 on Food stating that in realizing food availability, the government can increase domestic food production through:

- a. Develop food production that relies on local resources, institutions, and cultures.
- b. Develop the efficiency of the food business system.
- c. Develop facilities, infrastructure, and technology for production, post-harvest handling, processing, and storage of food.
- d. Build, rehabilitate, and develop food production infrastructure.
- e. Maintain and develop the productive land.
- f. Building a food production center.

Increased local production of food made by the government will meet the needs of the food for the people of Serang City. Efforts to increase local food production can be done by the Government of Serang City, given based on data of food security from the Serang City Agriculture Institution mentioned that the use of Serang City area for agriculture is wide enough that the use of agricultural land (wetland) type of irrigation is the largest land area of 4,910 ha of the total area of 8,355 ha. As for the use of agricultural land instead of rice fields tegal/garden is the largest with 6,406 ha of the total area of 11,747 ha. This should be a capital for Government of Serang City in utilizing the existing land, in order to increase local food production. However, people who depend on the agricultural sector only 7.77 percent, which means only 20,042 people from 257,861 people in Serang City. This should be the attention of the City Government, because with the lack of human resources moving in the agricultural sector, will also result in the decline in local food production and the decrease of food reserves of the Serang City Government, due to the availability of food related to increasing local food production and government food reserves. So in fulfillment of Government need to pay attention both of those things.

Increased production of local food will have a positive effect in terms of the food business in the region, in this case, is Serang City. The development of food business system that has been done by the Government of Serang City is making Community Food Barns (LPM). LPM was formed due to the many problems related to food faced by the community such as poverty, uncertain harvests, and climate problems, it needs food business to meet the food which needed to the people who are close and can be managed by the community themselves. In this case, the people who manage the LPM are the people who are members of the farmer group. The Government Serang City will provide the initial stimulant in the implementation of the community food business system. The system in LPM is similar to the savings and loans system in the cooperative, the loan in LPM can be in the form of rice or grain. So that the members of the farmer group who will borrow some grain or rice, will have to repay the loan with the same amount but give more with its power. With the existence of LPM program from the Government of Serang City can develop food business system in Serang City.

The fulfillment of the need for food is not only through the development of the food business system, but also the development of facilities, infrastructure, and technology for the production of post-harvest handling, processing, and storage of food. Serang City Government plays a role in the management of food reserves both government food reserves and community food reserves. The management of the government's food reserves and food reserves of the District/City people is implemented by the Regional Device Work Unit (SKPD) which performs the tasks and performs the functions in the field of food security. This is based on the mandate of Article 18 paragraph (2) of Government Regulation No. 17 of 2015 on Food Security and Nutrition, in this case, the District/City Government in the implementation can also be carried out in cooperation with State-Owned Enterprises and/or Regional-Owned Enterprises in the field of food. In the regulation, it has been clearly mentioned that in terms of management of food reserves to realize food availability in Serang City. Based on data from the Serang City Agricultural Service, it is known that to meet the needs of the community the Serang City Government imports and procures the needs from outside the region, as in the procurement of rice supply mostly obtained from Karawang, Kediri, Lampung, and Cianjur, Private company in Cigading, supply of chicken eggs obtained from Java, Sumatra, Pabuaran, and Petir, and supply of chicken obtained from Anyer, Lampung, Labuan, Pandeglang, and

⁷Ikomatussuniah, *Penguatan Fungsi Perusahaan Umum (PERUM) BULOG Berdasarkan Undang-undang Pangan*, Majalah Dinamika, Vol. 39 No. 2, Dinamika Triwulan 2, 2015, Serang, pages. 32.

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Mandalawangi. The results of research to big traders in Serang City tend to market more rice in Serang City because the existing supply is only focused to meet the needs of rice in Serang City. The rice that goes to Serang City is not all sold in the markets of Serang City and outside the Serang City area, but there are also some big traders supplying rice to the restaurant industry of 7,500 kg per month.¹⁰ New staple food that can be reserved by the Government of Serang City currently only rice, it is based on data obtained from the Institution of Agriculture of Serang City. Other efforts that have been done by the Government of Serang City is counseling-extension for farmer groups, whether related to harvest or post-harvest. However, the extension can only be done to farmers of farmer group members only. This is also an effort made by the City Government of Serang in the development of food production facilities and infrastructure that is building, rehabilitating, and developing existing food production infrastructure.

The development of food production infrastructure is also related to maintaining and developing the productive land. In Serang City the basic food production infrastructure is agricultural land, so its development is focused on the development of food agriculture land. The Government of Serang City in the development of productive land, the current regulation is still referring to the Regional Regulation of Banten Province No. 5 of 2014 on Sustainable Agricultural Land Protection. With the development of food production area can build food center area in Serang City, this matter is shown to make easy the society in fulfilling the requirement of food complete in the central area of food production. But at this time the food production center in Serang City has not focused on one food production area, and still divided in several places such as Kramatwatu, Pasar Rawu, and Walantaka. So it takes the efforts of Serang City Government to realize the availability of food production center area in Serang City.

Inadequate implementation in realizing food availability in Serang City, shows that the Serang City Agriculture Institution doesn't exercise its authority received by attribution in the provisions of Article 12 paragraph (2) of Law No. 18 of 2012 on Food as is, stating that the government and Local governments are responsible for the availability of food and the development of local food production in the region. Implementation in realizing food security in Serang City which is currently implemented by the Institution of Agriculture of Serang City, based on the mandate in article 3 letter d of Serang City Regulation No. 7 of 2016 on the Establishment and Composition of Serang City Device, stating that the Institution of Agriculture held government affairs In agriculture, marine and fisheries, and food field.

The mandate of Law No. 18 of 2012 on Food, is *Lex Specialis Derogated Lex Generalis* with the Regulation of the Minister of Agriculture of the Republic of Indonesia Number 43/Permentan/OT.010/8/2016 on Guidelines of Nomenclature, Duties, and Functions of Food Affairs and Agricultural Affairs Institution District/City Province. In the regulation issued by the Minister of Agriculture of the Republic of Indonesia, it is mentioned that the regional apparatus of the District/City which is the implementing element of the District/City government administration for the food affairs in the form of the District/City Service based on Article 2 paragraph (2) Regulation of the Minister of Agriculture of the Republic of Indonesia No. 43/Permentan/OT.010/8/2016 concerning the Nomenclature Guidelines, Duties and Functions of Food Affairs and the Institution of Agricultural Affairs of the Province of the District/City. It is also mentioned in Article 5 paragraph (2) that the nomenclature of the District/City named by the Institution, providing food affairs as referred to in Article 2 paragraph (2) is called the District Food Security Institution. With the absence of Food Security Service in Serang City, the implementation of food security affairs currently implemented by the Serang City Agriculture Institution isn't as it should be. Implementation of food availability in Serang City isn't maximal in the absence of special institutions that handle food security affairs. In Attachment III of Regulation of the Minister of Agriculture of the Republic of Indonesia No. 43/Permentan/OT.010/8/2016 mentions the duties and functions of the District Food Security Institution, such as:

- a. Preparation of regional policies in the areas of food availability, food insecurity, food distribution, food reserves, diversification of consumption and food security.
- b. Implementation of local policies in the areas of food availability, food insecurity, food distribution, food reserves, diversification of consumption and food security.
- c. Coordination of the provision of infrastructure and support in the areas of food availability, food insecurity, food distribution, food reserves, diversification of consumption and food security.
- d. Improving the quality of human resources in the areas of food availability, food insecurity, food distribution, food reserves, diversification of consumption and food security.
- e. Monitoring, supervision, evaluation, and reporting of funds in the field of food availability, food insecurity, food distribution, food reserves, diversification of consumption and food security.

⁸Bambang Hendro Sunarmito, *Pertanian Terpadu untuk Mendukung Kedaulatan Pangan Nasional*, Gadjah Mada University Press, Yogyakarta, 2014, pages. 42.

⁹Salim, *Pembkab Genjot Target Swasembada Pangan*, Majalah Dina2mika Kabupaten Serang, Vol. 40 No. 1, Dinamika Triwulan 1, 2016, Serang, pages. 35.

¹⁰Serang City Agriculture Institution, Mrs. Andriyani Head of Food Division, 27/03/2017.

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- f. Implementation of administration of Food Security Institution.
- g. Implementation of other functions provided by the Regent/Mayor.
Based on the duties and functions of the Minister of Agriculture Regulation, there are several things that have been implemented by the Institution of Agriculture of Serang City. But the implementation is not optimal, including:
 - a. Inadequate supervision and monitoring in terms of food safety in Serang City, seen from the monitoring of food safety are only done once a year or before the holiday.
 - b. Implementation of regional policies in the field of food availability is not accomplished maximally because Serang City currently only has a draft of Serang City Regulation on Food Security.
- c. Based on the data obtained, shows that the District/City in Banten Province has all have District Food Security Agency District/City except Serang City. Serang City Government, in this case, does not implement the provisions of the function related to the provision of infrastructure and support in the field of food security, because it does not implement the provisions in the Ministry of Agriculture Regulation as appropriate.

2. Food Security Institution

The concept of food security contains four essences, which become a barometer of food security, namely food availability, food accessibility, food stability, and food quality. All these essences are an integrated system and cannot be beheaded, established one by one. The availability of food will be meaningless, if the quality of food is not accountable, for example too much toxic or not kosher. Good food quality will be meaningless when it is not accessible, either because of exclusive price or distribution. Food stability also never comes true when there isn't an intensive relationship between various food and peasant stakeholders.¹¹ Food security in the Food Law is a condition of the fulfillment of food for the state up to the individual, which is reflected in the availability of adequate food, both quantity and quality, safe, diverse, nutritious, equitable, and affordable and not contrary to religion, conviction, and community culture, to be able to live healthy, active, and productive. So based on that, the local government has a responsibility to realize food security in the region. Since the important aspect of food security is sustainability, it is necessary to have an institution that plays a role in food security, both hierarchically from central to local and institutional level from the subsystem of availability, distribution, to consumption. Governments and communities alike have a responsibility in realizing food security as mandated in food related laws. There are many institutions with an interest in food security, both governmental, private, and public. These institutions can be said to be sufficient, it's just necessary strengthening the functions and roles of these institutions, to be more effective and efficient performance. Thus, effectively and efficiently the performance of institutions related to food security especially in the regions, can increase the achievement of food security in the area.

Special institutions dealing with issues related to food security in the respective jurisdictions shall be in the form of the Food Security Service, this is in a line with the mandate of Regulation the Minister of Agriculture Republic of Indonesia Number 43/Permentan/OT.010/8/2016 concerning the Nomenclature Guidelines, Duties and Functions of the Service Food Affairs and Regional Agricultural Affairs Institution of District/City. Mention that the regional apparatus of District/City that handles food affairs is in the form of the District/City Institution, then it is mentioned also that the nomenclature of the agency that organizes the affairs in the field of food is called the District Food Security Institution. This special institution has the main duty and function that must be implemented in an effort to realize food security in the region, therefore it is appropriate for every region to have food security Institution, and do not give the dense duty to other institution/Institution to carry out duties and functions of organizing food security. To solve food problems that can trigger other problems from different sectors.

In Serang City the population increase also happens annually at 1.92 percent. With the increase of population, agriculture land conversion also occurs, given the increasing need of the community for clothing, food, and boards. Serang community consumption level on staple food also increased, this can be seen from the amount of demand for rice in 2016 of 64,281 tons from the previous rice demand in 2015 only 1360 tons.¹² So the role of Serang City Government in the effort of food security in the region at least can provide solutions for these problems, especially in meeting the increasing food needs of the community. Based on the activities that have been done by of Serang City Agriculture Institution, it can be seen that the number of programs implemented is the grant of goods to the community groups in the field of agriculture, plantation and fishery. By conducting grants to other granary groups, the hope to be achieved is the fulfillment of food needs of the community. The assistance provided by the Serang City Agriculture Institution is an initial stimulant, to be developed to ensure that food availability is always present and increasing in number, so that the needs of the community, especially those incorporated in certain groups of agriculture, plantations and fisheries can be fulfilled.

¹¹Bambang Hendro Sunarmito, *Op. Cit*, pages. 27.

¹²Serang City Agriculture Institution, *Op. Cit*.

¹³Interview with Mrs. Andriyani Head of Food Division, Tuesday 02/04/2017, 15.00 WIB, at Serang City Agricultural Institution.

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However, in practice, many stimulants are given away without any addition of initial stock given by the Government of Serang City. This can be interpreted that the role made by the Serang City Agriculture Institution in terms of guidance for the community food barns who receive the grant is not maximal. The non-optimal role of the Serang City Agricultural Institution can also be seen from the availability of food in Serang City, which comes from local production can not meet the needs of the community. So it is necessary to have special institutions that deal with issues related to food security to perform tasks and functions in the field of food security to the maximum.

Efforts made by the Serang City Agriculture Institution in realizing the availability of food is an effort made to realize food security in the Serang City. In the implementation, there are constraints faced. Based on interviews with the Head of Food Division of Serang City Agriculture Institution, said that the constraint is the limited budget that is owned by the Institution of Agriculture for the implementation of various food security programs so that the programs have been implemented are not maximized.¹³ Efforts made such as grant goods for community food groups in agriculture, plantation, and fishery are not maximal with the least amount of grants given. Limited budget and limitations of human resources in the internal SKPD become the main obstacle of Serang City Agriculture Institution in organizing food security in the region. Given the basic tasks and functions of food security, it is found in the main tasks and functions of the Serang City Agricultural Institution, so that the budget allocation for the food security program isn't maximal in its implementation. This shows that the Serang City government needs to make other efforts in terms of food/agricultural politics. Politics in the sense of fundamental policy as a reference for the long term, meaning that food security programs should be done by the government Institution that specifically handles food problems.¹⁴ Another obstacle in the implementation of food security in Serang City, which isn't maximized management of food management by the Serang City Agriculture Institution. This can be seen from the insufficient development of local production in realizing the availability of food in Serang City so that in the supply must from outside the region. With good food management despite the limited budget, food security in Serang City can still be realized. Another obstacle is not the diversity of food reserves that are owned by the Government of Serang City and the community, this is as stated by the Head of Food Division of Serang City Agriculture Institution, that the main food that can be reserved in Serang City is only rice.

Many obstacles faced by the Serang City Agricultural Institution in organizing food security, shows that the Serang City Agricultural Institution cannot implement the implementation of food security in essence. This can also result in the availability of food for the community, as there are three sub- systems in food security: food availability, food accessibility, and food security. If in the case of food availability cannot be implemented by the Government of Serang City, then other sub-systems will not be executed by the Government of Serang City itself. Because the availability of food can be used as a benchmark in the implementation of food security in an area. Because the availability of food in an area will facilitate the people in the area to meet the need for food, as well as in the city of Serang. If the Government of Serang City has maximized the availability of food through the development of local food in the area, then the people of Serang City don't need to supply food from outside the Serang City area. This, of course, will also affect the welfare of the community both farmers and ordinary people.

This food security institution solely aims to implement state duties in the ICESCR Convention 2010 related to food security, which the task of the state is to protect, to respect, and to fulfill. In this case, the fulfillment of the right to food is a state duty that must be implemented by the government. So the Food Security Institution can be an institution to fulfill the task because in this case, the government has done prevention to its citizens from the inability of its citizens in meeting the needs of their food.¹⁵

CONCLUSION

The conclusion of this study is that the role of local government in the availability of food in Serang city is the authority accepted attribution through article 12 paragraph (2) of Law Number 18 the Year 2012 on Food, noted that food availability is the responsibility of the Government and Local Government. In matters relating to the availability of food based on the mandate of

¹⁴Eko Suksmantri Dkk, *Bulog Dalam Bingkai Ketahanan Pangan*, Padma Publisher, Jakarta, 2012, pages. 360.

¹⁵Asbjorn Eide, *State Obligations for Human Rights: the Case of the Right to Food*, in the Book *Governing Food Security*, ed: Otto Hospes dan Irene Hardiprayitno, Wageningen Academic Publishers, pages. 115.

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Article 18 paragraph (2) of Government Regulation No. 17 Year 2015 on Food Security and Nutrition, stated that in the implementation of food reserve District/City Government implemented by the Regional Work Units (SKPD) that perform the task or performs functions In the field of food security. Serang City Agriculture Institution is now an SKPD who have authority in food security, but given the duties and functions of the Institution of Agriculture Serang City pretty solid, it would require an independent Institution in charge of food security affairs. It is based on the mandate in Article 5, paragraph (2) of the Regulation the Minister of Agriculture Republic of Indonesia Number 43/Permentan/OT.010/8/2016 on Guidelines for Nomenclature, Duties, and Functions Affairs Institution of Food and Agricultural Affairs Office of the Provincial and District/City, stating That the nomenclature of the District/City Institution that administers food affairs is called the District Food Security Institution. So that in the absence of an independent institution whose duties and functions related to food security, the Government of Serang City didn't implement this Regulation the Minister of Agriculture Republic of Indonesia Number 43/Permentan/OT.010/8/2016 on Guidelines for Nomenclature, Duties, and functions of the Institution of Food Affairs And Provincial and District/City Provincial Agricultural Affairs Institution appropriately.

Constraints to the provision of food in the effort to implement food security in Serang City, such as budget constraints, poor management of food management, insufficient internal human resources of SKPD that implement food security, understanding of diverse foods. Talking about food security is very extensive, not just in the agricultural sector. Based on article 1 number 1 of Law No. 18 of 2012 on Food, namely food is anything that comes from biological sources of agricultural products, plantations, forestry, fisheries, livestock, water, and water, whether processed or not processed as food or drinks for human consumption. Therefore the problems in the food security sector is a more complex problem than the problems in the agricultural sector. So if the problem related to food security is only handled by the Agriculture Institution, then other obstacles cannot be handled maximally by the Institution in solving the problem of food security in Serang City. In food security has sub system that must be fulfilled that is food availability, food access, and food safety. The most common problem is related to the availability of food, so the solution of food availability problem must be prioritized. If the sub-availability of food is not held maximally, then in the implementation of other sub-systems are not optimal.

SUGGESTION

The suggestion in this study is that the problem of food security should be handled seriously, given the increasing population growth almost every year, the need for food increases. An independent institution in charge of food security is required, in line with the mandate of Article 5 paragraph (2) of Regulation the Minister of Agriculture Republic of Indonesia No. 43/Permentan/OT.010/8/2016 concerning Guidelines on Nomenclature, Duties, and Functions of Food Affairs and Provincial and District/City Agricultural Affairs Institution, stated that the nomenclature of the District/City Institution that organizes the food affairs is called the District Food Security Institution. So that in the implementation of food availability implemented by the Government of Serang City will be implemented maximally with the Regional Device Work Unit (SKPD) that specifically address issues related to food security. Given in Banten Province only Serang City which until now hasn't special SKPD to handle food security issues.

Food availability includes national food reserves, local food production, and imports of the two main sources are not sufficient for food. Increasing local food production needs to be done by the Serang City Agricultural Institution, given the main staple food source of Serang City is mostly obtained from areas outside Serang City. This will be related to the food reserves of the Local Government, considering that the new staple food of Serang City can only be reserved at present only rice. Since the main food source of the community is mostly obtained from outside the region, the increase in local food production can help diversify the types of food in the food reserves of the Local Government.

REFERENCES

Journal

- 1) Ikomatussuniah. (2013). *Class Action terhadap Utang Swasta Bantuan Likuidasi Bank Indonesia menjadi Utang Negara*. Jurnal Masalah-masalah Hukum ISSN 2086- 2695. Vol. 42 No 3. hlm. 363.
- 2) Ikomatussuniah. (2016). *Letargi Harga Pangan*. Majalah Dinamika Kabupaten Serang.Vol. 40 No. 3 Dinamika Triwulan 3. hlm. 38.
- 3) Ikomatussuniah. (2015). *Penguatan Fungsi Perusahaan Umum (PERUM) BULOG Berdasarkan Undang-undang Pangan*. Majalah Dinamika, Vol. 39 No. 2 Dinamika Triwulan 2. hlm. 32.
- 4) Salim. (2016). *Pembkab Genjot Target Swasembada Pangan*. Majalah Dinamika Kabupaten Serang. Vol. 40 No. 1 Dinamika Triwulan 1. hlm. 35.

Book

- 1) Asbjorn Eide. *State Obligations for Human Rights: the Case of the Right to Food*. In the Book of Governing Food Security. Ed: Otto Hospes dan Irene Hardiprayitno. Wageningen Academic Publishers.

Role of Local Government in Food Availability Based on Indonesia's Food Law in Serang City

- 2) Badan Pusat Statistik. *Banten Dalam Angka 2016*.
- 3) Bambang Hendro Sunarmito. (2014). *Pertanian Terpadu untuk Mendukung Kedaulatan Pangan Nasional*. Gadjah Mada University Press. Yogyakarta.
- 4) Christine S. T. Kansil. (2004). *Pemerintahan Daerah di Indonesia Hukum Administrasi Negara*. Sinar Grafika. Jakarta.
- 5) Eko Suksmantri Dkk. (2012). *Bulog Dalam Bingkai Ketahanan Pangan*. Padma Publisher. Jakarta.
- 6) Lexy J. Moleong. (2012). *Metodologi Penelitian Kualitatif*. Remaja Rosdakarya. Bandung.
- 7) R. Abdoel Djamali. (2012). *Pengantar Hukum Indonesia edisi revisi*. Jakarta: Rajawali Pers.
- 8) Soemitro, R. H. (1992). *Metodologi Penelitian Hukum*. Jakarta. Ghalia Indonesia. Zainuddin Ali, M. (2013). *Metode Penelitian Hukum*. Jakarta. Sinar Grafika.

Minithesis

- 1) Widiatul Arafah. (2017). *Peran Pemerintah Daerah Dalam Ketersediaan Pangan di Kota Serang Dihubungkan Dengan Undang-undang Nomor 18 Tahun 2012 tentang Pangan*. Serang. Sultan Ageng Tirtayasa University.

Internet

- 1) Swasembada Pangan Untuk Ketahanan Pangan. <http://ikomatussuniah-design.blogspot.co.id/>. Accesible on 07/07/2017. 07.17.